

Supplementary Figure 1. **A-B** – visualizations of a fumigation chamber method for collecting ectoparasites of birds. **B** – examination of the head of the bird during the fumigation process. White dots on the head feathers are louse eggs. **C** – capturing and recording louse behavior using a portable microscope camera (field experiment).

Supplementary Figure 2. The variability in surface temperatures between different body parts of bird host individuals. (n = 78, except neck surface temperature, which was taken only from 11

individuals). **A** – a violin plot for visualization of individual values and their distribution. Red dots indicate the mean values and white lines indicate 95% confidence interval. **B** – Tukey HSD post hoc comparison. Horizontal lines that do not touch vertical red line (dashed) represent significant differences ($p < 0.5$) in mean temperature.

Supplementary Figure 3. The body mass of the bird host individuals and its relation to the surface temperature variability of different body parts of the bird hosts ($n = 78$, except neck surface temperature, which was taken only from 11 individuals). The “X” marks represent the mean values.

Supplementary Figure 4. Correlation between the body mass and surface temperatures of different body parts of the bird individuals. Values 0-0.2 (head, underwing, and neck) could be considered as very weak correlation; and 0.2-0.4 (back and belly) as weak correlation.